

m. p. 284°. When heated to about 260°-270° in a metal bath chloroumbelliferone began to sublime as colourless prisms, m. p. 271° (mixed m. p. with 6-chloroumbelliferone, the condensation product of 4-chlororesorcin with malic acid is also 271°).

In conclusion our grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for giving full facilities to carry on this investigation.

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A Semi-micro Method of Determining Total Nitrogen of Air-dry Soils.

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The present investigation was undertaken with a view to find out if Pregl's Micro-Kjeldahl method (Fritz Pregl, "Die Quantitative Organische Micro Analyse," 1930, p. 120) could be applied in the determination of the total nitrogen of soils and thus to save time and reagents otherwise necessary for the macro method. In the micro method, it is impossible to work with 3-5 mg. (of the soil) which is the amount usually employed in micro analyses of pure organic compounds due to the almost negligible amount of ammonia that would be obtained. Hence 0.5 g. of the soil was found to be the suitable quantity. Elimination of sampling error, however, is to be carefully guarded against. An experiment was carried out with stock soil to test the method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

About 1 lb of soil was sieved through a 1 mm. sieve and a sub-sample containing about 50 g. was made in the usual way. The sub-sample was thoroughly ground in an agate mortar and sieved through a 30 mesh sieve, the process of grinding being repeated until all the soils passed through the sieve. Now the finely ground soil was spread over a glazed paper in thin layer and mixed thoroughly. With the help of a fine nickel spatula, about 0.5 g. of soil taken from different places was weighed in micro weighing bottles, and taken in a micro Kjeldahl digestion flask and about 0.5 g. of sodium sulphate

containing a trace of copper sulphate together with 1 c. c. of water and 2 c. c. of concentrated sulphuric acid. The mixture was then digested in the usual way for about one hour after which it was cooled and 1 c. c. of water added. The digested mass was then transferred to the micro distillation flask and the distillation of ammonia carried out in the apparatus of Parnas and Wagner fully described by Pregl (*loc. cit.*, p. 123). The volume of distilled water employed to transfer the digested mass to the distillation flask was 15 c.c., 10 c.c. of 50% caustic soda solution were employed to make the acid solution in the distillation flask alkaline and the distillation was carried out for 8 minutes. During the last minute of distillation, the end of the silver tube was raised slightly above the level of the standard acid solution in the quartz receiver. A series of estimations was carried out. The results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Quantity of soil (g.) ...	0.5225	0.5305	0.5699	0.5150
Nitrogen (%) ...	0.0927	0.0922	0.0926	0.0919
			Mean	0.0924
By macro method				0.0933

It is clear from the above table that there is a good agreement between the individual micro determinations indicating thereby that the sampling error has practically been eliminated. Further the small difference between the micro and macro determinations lies within the limits of experimental error. Next the determination of total nitrogen of Dacca and Faridpur soil was carried out and the results obtained are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Soil.	Method of estimation.	Nitrogen.	Mean.
Faridpur (alluvial)	Micro	0.0625%	0.0623
		0.0620	
Dacca (laterite)	Macro	0.0627	0.0955
	Micro	0.0958	
		0.0952	
	Macro	0.0960	

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